

Effect of Training in Creative Thinking Skills on Educational Psychology to Achievement of Tertiary Education Students

Chidinma E. Okwara-Kalu, Ph.D

Department of Educational Psychology/G&C,

Alvan Ikoku Federal University of Education, Owerri, Imo State, Nigeria

Annabel U. Obinna-Akakuru, Ph.D ✉

Department of Educational Psychology/G&C,

Alvan Ikoku Federal University of Education, Owerri, Imo State, Nigeria

Josephine N. Ipem, Ph.D

Department of Educational Psychology/G&C,

Alvan Ikoku Federal University of Education, Owerri, Imo State, Nigeria

Azukaego I. Eluemuno, Ph.D

Department of Educational Psychology/G&C,

Alvan Ikoku Federal University of Education, Owerri, Imo State, Nigeria

Timothy N. Nwanorim, Ph.D

Department of Curriculum & Instructions,

Alvan Ikoku Federal University of Education, Owerri, Imo State, Nigeria

Abstract

This study investigated the effect of training in creative thinking skills on Educational Psychology II achievement of tertiary education students. The study adopted a pre-test, posttest and control design. Four research questions and two hypotheses guided the study. The undergraduate Creative Thinking Questionnaire (UNCTQ) was employed in data collection. The instrument was developed by the researchers and it had two items bordering on creativity and critical thinking. It has a ceiling point of 100%. Undergraduates who scores less than 50% were selected through randomization for the study. The objective of selecting them was to teach them creative thinking skills. The UNCTQ was used at pre-test before the training exercise. UNCTQ-1 which was reshuffled after the six weeks training on creative thinking was the second instrument which served as a post-test instrument. The instrument was validated by specialists and was determined to have reliability coefficients of 0.71 and 0.80. Data collected was analyzed in two domains: Descriptive statistics was employed in answering the research questions whereas analysis of co-variance (ANCOVA) was employed in testing the hypotheses formulated. The study found that participants in convergent treatment group had improved achievement mean score at posttest assessment; those in divergent thinking treatment group improved and higher achievement mean score at posttest and that those in inspirational thinking skill group obtained a higher achievement mean score at posttest. The study therefore recommends as follows: that

training in creative thinking be encouraged in all tiers of education in Nigeria, using the techniques of convergent, divergent and inspirational thinking skills etc.

Keywords: *Training, Creativity Thinking Skills, Educational Psychology II Achievement and Tertiary Education Students.*

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Introduction

The place of creative thinking skills in the 21st century cannot be overemphasized. Given the influx of knowledge and the technological demands of this century, it has become extremely necessary for students to be equipped with a high sophisticated skill of thinking that match the technological knowhow of the time. In the 21st century, creativity thinking has attracted much attention because of its obvious demands. Chen and Kaufman cited in Campbell (2021) submit that the most important economic resource in the 21st century is creativity thinking skills. Zhao still in Campbell avers that employees in the 21st century should be creative thinkers and not routine workers who are known for recycling ideas and maintaining status quo. (Kampylis and Berki, (2014) describe creativity as an active process necessarily involved in innovation. They equally view it as a learning process or habit in which students require skills and specific understanding of the creative context in which creativity can be applied. Creativity also has defined as one's intellectual ability to reason differently and uniquely with a view to finding solutions or answers to a given problem or situations (Harris (2014; Saccardi (2014) and Wang, Peck, Chern (2010).

Creativity thinking points one to many solutions to felt problems. It also develops one's ability to perceive novel solutions to problems. Wool (2021) agrees that creative thinking is very necessary as it saves one from routine thought patterns that makes productivity ineffective. Mahama, Kwaw, Mensah, Acheampong and Marfo (2019) further observe that creative thinking is indispensable in that it is part and parcel of everyday activities of people. Reid and Pteocz cited in Mahama, Kwaw, Mensah, Acheampong and Marfo (2019) submit that creativity thinking results in the production of tangible objects such as artworks, books, music, as well as buildings, machines, or devices; it equally involves ideas, processes, services or systems of operation, production and delivery. In addition, they maintained that creativity encompasses doing things in a novel and effective ways. It is therefore imperative that students are encouraged to develop the ability to think creatively.

Creative thought involves the ability of one in this case, a student to use different thinking styles and examining issues from different perspectives in order to generate new ideas and patterns handling them. To develop this ability, the teacher should constantly engage students in the use of brainstorming strategies and other

metacognitive instructional approaches. It is very unfortunate that most of creativity thinking strategies are not in use in most schools because many teachers are yet to develop the skills themselves. There are many types of innovative creative thinking skills a teacher can foster in the classroom.

Among the creative thinking skills that should be taught to learners are aesthetic thinking, divergent thinking, lateral thinking, convergent thinking and inspirational thinking. The most commonly used among them are divergent and convergent thinking (Wool, 2021). Through divergent thinking one can generate as many possible solutions to a felt problem as possible. Whereas convergent thinking has to do with being logical; a situation where one gathers facts about an issue and uses them to proffer solutions to a particular problem. Both thinking skills complement each other in problem solving (Wool, 2021). Inspirational Thinking has to do with imagining the problem situation with a view to drawing inspiration to find a new way of solving it; Lateral thinking is to think and allow ideas flow systematically. Aesthetic thinking involves reordering, framing or reorganizing issues (ideas) or objects such that their inherent beauty and value are perceived and this leads to the generation of new ideas.

Having creative thinking skills distinguishes one among others in any field of endeavour. For instance, most employers seek people with creative minds and this could be the reason for the massive unemployment in the country as most of the educational institutions in the country churn out each year job seekers that are not creatively oriented. Fostering creative writing entails being curious over felt problems. Curiosity helps one to be up and doing. It has helped many to discover new ideas and to solve unimaginable problems. A curious person asks so many questions at a time. It helps one to identify the right problem in the many confusing problems. It is believed that training students in creative thinking skills will make them versatile in finding solutions to their academic, social and psychological problems. For this study, students here refer specifically to students in tertiary Institutions. Training in creative thinking skills promises to distinguish them remarkably from others in many ways - academic performance, problem solving, stronger interpersonal connections, heightened productivity, higher self-awareness among others.

Developing a strong creative thinking among tertiary institution students, involves practicing different think styles, strategies and brainstorming with fellow students, meeting with new people other than those they have been with and allowing boredom set in. Boredom for instance creates opportunity to think in order to get out of it. Also, students could be encouraged to be inquisitive about everything that is of interest to them and to try finding possible answers to them. Doing the above demands a whole lot of efforts; practice they say, makes perfect. Students under training should be helped to identify solutions and patterns that were not originally seen as that can set one out as a better problem solver and as well earn one better rewards.

Creative thinkers always challenge their beliefs, assumptions, perspectives and this helps them to improve on previous knowledge (Wool, 2021). Sac and Maker (2006) state that teachers have greater responsibility to inculcate or train students on the use of creative thinking skills. Adeyemi and Oladele (2020) carried out a study on creative thinking ability and academic performance in core subjects of lower primary school pupils in which they sought to determine the difference in the academic performance of pupils of different levels of creative thinking ability with a view to providing information on how pupils' creative thinking ability could bring about a better academic performance of lower primary school pupils in core areas. The study among other findings concluded that creative thinking ability of lower primary school pupils

brought about enhanced performance in core subjects. Going by the findings of this study, it is hopeful that exposure to creativity thinking skills could enhance academic achievement of tertiary institution students in Educational Psychology II.

This study also ascertained if gender was a factor to be considered in the development of creative thinking skills in tertiary institution students. Usually it is mostly believed that men think more than women. Women are too emotional about things. Is that true? Can it be said that men are more rational than ladies? The study by Mahama, Kwaw, Mensah, Acheampong and Marfo (2019) on the relationship between creative thinking and students' academic performance in English Language and Mathematics on the moderating role of gender, revealed among others significant relationship between creative thinking and academic performance of students. It also revealed that gender moderated significantly in the relationship between creative thinking skills and academic performance of students in English Language: male respondents had higher creative thinking effect in English Language and Mathematics than female students. This study may prove otherwise. Who knows?

Educational Psychology is an applied branch of Psychology which borrows psychological assumptions, theories and principles from psychology which is a pure science and apply them in educational settings with a view to solving the problems of teaching and learning. Educational Psychology I is one of the courses taken by year 1 students who are studying for degree programme in Alvan Ikoku Federal College of Education, Owerri, Nigeria. This course exposes the learner to the processes involved in studying human development and behaviour. It aims at understanding, describing, controlling and predicting behaviour for future use. It is expected that exposing year one students to this course will help broaden their horizon about themselves, others and their physical environment thereby motivating them to think of ways of enhancing themselves physically, academically, socially, intellectually and psychologically. It is then necessary to begin at this point to develop their thinking skills.

Statement of the Problem

It is commonly said that, Nigerians do not think or reason before taking actions. Many also have assumed that schools in the country churn out applicants who do not have creative minds; hence they find it difficult to apply what they studied at school in work places as well as solve life's problems. The above makes many of them unemployable.

Again, most students seem to be over dependent on their teachers and fellow students when it comes to doing class assignments and passing examinations. They hardly can solve minor academic problems: hence, they resort to exam malpractice and other vices for grades. Lack of creative thinking skills could be responsible for low grades which characterizes many tertiary institution students. It also seems that many students fail Educational Psychology I and other courses probably because of the instructional strategies they are exposed to.

Though, many studies have been carried out on effects of some instructional strategies on academic performance but none has been done training in creativity and Educational Psychology I of students. The researchers therefore had this hunch that training in creativity skills could enhance the Educational Psychology I achievement of tertiary institution students and as well as improve their problem solving skills. It is on this premise that they set out to ascertain the effect of creative thinking skills on the Educational Psychology I of tertiary education students.

To guide the study, the following research questions and hypotheses were formulated:

1. What is the effect of Convergent creative thinking skill on Educational Psychology I achievement students at pretest and posttest?
2. What is the effect of Divergent Creative thinking skill on Educational Psychology I achievement of students at pretest and posttest?
3. What is the effect of Inspiration creative thinking on Educational Psychology I achievement of students at pretest and posttest?
4. What is the mean difference between the male and female students expose to creative thinking skills and those not exposed to it at pretest and posttest?

Ho1: There is no significant difference in the mean score of students in the three creative thinking skill groups at posttest.

Ho2: There is no significant difference in the mean scores of the male and female students exposed to the three creative thinking skills at posttest.

Method

The study adopted a pre-test, posttest and control approach to determine effect of creative thinking slates on Education psychology achievement of undergraduates. The design is adequate because Quasi-experimental approach is enshrined in cause and effect of variables being manipulated outside. The population of the study was 600 undergraduates in year two the sample of the study was 10% of the population which has 120 male and female undergraduates in year II in Alvan Ikoku Federal College of Education. Undergraduate Creative Thinking Questionnaire was employed in data collection (UNCTQ) has the instrument was developed by the Research and it had two item bordering on creativity and critical thinking. It has a ceiling point of 100%. Undergraduates who scores less than 50% were selected through randomization for the study. The objective of selecting them was to teach them creative thinking skills the UNCTQ was used at pre-test before the training exercise. UNCTQ-1 which was reshuffled after the six weeks training on creative thinking was the score instrument which served as a post-test instrument. The instrument was validated by specialists and was determined to have a reliability coefficient of 0.71 and 0.80. After the selection process through randomization, participants were subjected to a six weeks creativity training on three components of creativity namely: convergent creative thinking, divergent creative thinking and inspirational thinking. After six weeks a post-test was given to participants to determine the effect of the training on them via: UNCTQ-1. Data collected was analyzed in thro domains: Research question and hypotheses Descriptive statistics was employed in answering the research question whereas analysis of co-variance (ANCOVA) was employed in testing the hypotheses formulated.

Results

The results of the study were presented below:

Table 1. Difference in Mean and Standard Duration Scores of Participants Trained in Convergent Creative Thinking Skills at Pre-Test and Post-Test Assessment Periods

Variables	N	Pre-test X	Student Deviation	Post-test X	Student Deviation	Difference In Score
Convergent training group	30	34.20	6.421	55.24	2.31	32.04
Control Group	30	34.20	3.140	35.26	5.41	1.06

Table 1 shows the pre-test and post-test scores of participants in convergent thinking training and control groups. At pre-test both groups: convergent thinking groups scored 34.20 with a standard deviation score of 6.421 and control group had 34.20 with a standard deviation score of 3.140. At post-test, the convergent thinking training group scored a mean of 55.24 and standard deviation of 2.31 whereas control group had 35.26 as mean and 5.41 as standard deviation.

The standard deviation of the treatment group at pre-test (6.421) reflects a wide margin and uneven distribution of scores obtained while at post-test the scores were evenly distributed.

Table 2. Difference in Mean and Standard Deviation Scores of Participants Trained in Divergent Creative Thinking Skills at Pre-Test and Post-Test Assessment Periods

Variables	N	Pre-test X	Student Deviation	Post-test X	Student Deviation	Difference In Score
Divergent training group	30	34.20	6.412	67.70	2.17	
Control Group	30	34.20	3.143	37.60	5.46	

Table 2 shows the pretest and post-test mean scores for participants in treatment and control groups. The pre-test scores were considered equal but after treatment in divergent thinking skills, the treatment group had a tremendous increase in mean score at post-test with an even distribution of the scores reflecting in standard deviation of 2.17. The control group at post-test had a slight increase of 3.40 points in the mean and an uneven distribution in standard deviation.

Table 3. Difference in Mean and Standard Deviation Scores of Participants Trained in Inspiration Creative Thinking Skills at Pre-Test and Post-Test Assessment Periods

Variables	N	Pre-test X	Student Deviation	Post-test X	Student Deviation	Difference In Score
Inspiration training group	30	34.20	6.21	62.74	2.16	28.54
Control Group	30	34.20	3.140	36.27	5.12	2.07

Table 3 shows the pre-test and post-test mean scores for participants in treatment groups and control where the same (34.20) however, there were variations in the standard deviation scores for treatment and control groups. At post-test the treatment group had a mean score of 62.74 and standard deviation score of 2.16. However, the control revealed remained almost the same (36.27) from (34.20). This revealed the effect of the treatment given on creative thinking skills.

Table 4. Difference in Mean and Standard Deviation Scores of Participants in Treatment Groups by Gender

Group	Gender	N	Pre-test		Post-test	
			X	Std. Dev	X	Std Dev
Convergent Group	Male	15	35.40	5.641	64.53	2.02
	Female	15	35.40	5.424	61.02	2.09
Divergent Group	Male	15	34.20	4.218	59.07	2.14
	Female	15	34.20	4.201	56.01	2.01
Inspiration Group	Male	15	34.15	5.102	61.03	2.63
	Female	15	34.18	5.107	60.04	2.02

From table 4, participants in convergent group had equal mean scores at pre-test and a slight variation in standard deviation. At post-test male participants scored 64.53 and standard deviation of 2.07, whereas female participants scored 61.02 as mean and standard deviation of 2.09. In Divergent group at post-test, male participants had 59.07 as mean and standard deviation of 2.14. Female participants had 56.01 as mean score and standard deviation of 2.01. In inspiration group, male participants had 61.03 as mean and standard deviation score of 2.63 at post-test, whereas female participants scored 61.03 as mean and standard deviation score of 2.63 at post-test, whereas female participants scored 61.03 as mean and standard deviation of 2.02.

Table 5. Analysis of Covariance (ANCOVA) on Mean Scores of Participants in Convergent, Divergent, Inspiration and Control at Pre-Test and Post-Test Assessment Period

Source	Type III Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig	Partial Eta Squared
Corrected Mode	19883.979	9	22009.331	169.602	.000	.822
Intercept	837.663	1	837.763	63.314	.000	.379
Pre-test	.394	1	.374	.020	.762	.000
Post-test	231.716	1	231.716	17.567	.000	1.34
Group	1289.276	3	326.419	31.638	.000	.462
Gender	43.432	1	43.432	3.257	.074	.227
Group Gender	36.908	3	12.025	.845	.421	.024
Error	1422.712	110	13.025			
Total	344687.000	120				
Corrected Total	21216.782	119				

Note: R-square = .937 (adjusted R-Squared = 927)

From table 4 labeled test of between subject effects, shows whether the groups (convergent, divergent, inspiration and control) are significantly different in terms of their scores on the achievement test of undergraduates in Educational Psychology II. The criterion value of 0.05 significant level is greater than the probability value of .000.

This suggests that the post-test effect is significant at 5% level of significance ($P < 0.05$). This contrasting values represents a significant difference among the three groups (convergent, divergent, inspiration and control). The hypothesis of no significant difference is rejected hence, there is a significant difference between the Educational Psychology II achievement mean score of participants in convergent, divergent, inspiration and control at post-test assessment period.

The table also shows the influence of covariate variables on the achievement mean scores in Educational Psychology II while controlling for the independent variable (groups). Here, it is .000 which is less than 0.05. therefore, the covariate, is significant and accounts for 93.7% of the variance in the dependent variable (R-squared .937 x 100). The difference in adjusted mean score of 0.005 revealed a minimal statistically measured effect of the covariates on the dependent variables.

Table 6: Analysis of Covariance (ANCOVA) on Educational Psychology Achievement Mean Scores of Participants in Convergent, Divergent, Inspiration and Control Groups by Gender after Training

Test of Between – Subjects affects Dependent Variable: Post-Test

Source	Type III Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig	Partial Eta Squared
Corrected Model	443.4369	6	72.734	4.171	.001	.230
Intercept	7421.255	1	7421.253	423.527	.000	.825
Pre-test	8.624	1	8.624	.485	.487	.006
Group	336.307	2	159.144	9.431	.000	.174
Gender	41.548	1	41.544	2.231	.130	.024
Group Gender	53.720	2	26.310	1.527	.210	.031
Error	1374.423	83	17.655			
Total	326026.000	90				
Corrected Total	1915.812	80				

Note: R-square = .230 (adjusted R-Squared = 165)

The table labeled ‘test of between subject affect’ shows that convergent, divergent, inspiration and control training groups by gender are significantly different in terms of their scores on the achievement test of undergraduates in Education psychology II. The significant difference observed is because the criterion value of 0.05 is less than the probability values of sig .000 on the table. These contrasting values signifies that the post-test effect is pronounced at 50% level of confidence ($P < 0.05$). Therefore, there is a significant difference among the three experimental groups (convergent, divergent, and inspiration) by gender. This main effect significant difference necessitated the rejection of no significant null hypothesis.

Table 6 also revealed the influence of the covariate variables on the achievement mean scores in variable psychology II while controlling for the independent variable (group) on the table. The probability value was .000 against 0.05 of the variance in the dependent value (R-squared .230 x 100%). The effect of the covariant of the three independent variables, convergent, divergent inspiration (convergent = 62.145⁹, Divergent = 58.422⁹ and inspiration = 60.231 respectively.

Discussion

The result of the study was that participants in convergent treatment group had an improved achievement mean achievement scores of participants in convergent treatment group at post-test was higher and better than their pre-test result undoubtedly would have been because of the convergent training in which participants were subjected to for a period 6 weeks assessment period. The result of this study is supported by Ugwulebo (2019) whose study on critical thinking revealed that students with higher critical thinking skills performed better in assessment test than others low in critical thinking skills.

The finding of the study was that participants in divergent thinking treatment group had an improved and higher achievement mean score that was obtained previously at pre-test and post-test. The result means that there was an improved performance in Educational Psychology II by participants after the training exercise that lasted for 6 weeks. The reason for the present finding would have been because of the divergent thinking exercise which participants were subjected for the period of six weeks. The divergent thinking skill training would have developed that thinking apparatus which resulted in a higher achievement mean score in Education psychology III at post-test. The result of this study is supported by the findings of Kwankwanzo (2017) whose study is study discovered an improvement on the academic performance of students after subjecting them to creative thinking skills.

The result of the study was that participants in inspirational thinking skill group obtained a higher achievement mean score in Education psychology III at post-test. This result means that participants in inspiration thinking skill group performed better in Education Psychology assessment test at post-test. In other words, participants in inspiration thinking group were better in achievement mean score at post-test. The reason for this result could be because of the inspirational training given to participants for a period of six weeks. The finding of this study was supported by Otolih (2018) whose study revealed that students subjected to inspirational training for a period of six weeks had higher achieve affective response during lessons.

Conclusion

The study established that creativity in its entirety affords educational advancements within the domain of Educational psychology. Convergent thinking which concentrates thoughts forms towards a problem situation and subsequent solution is encouraged among undergraduates in tertiary Educational. Divergent thinking which spreads thought forms in different angles for a possible solution to a problem state is through the finding of this study encouraged. Inspiration is innovative, hence, through the findings of the study improved the academic achievement of students in Educational psychology II.

It is therefore an important ingredient in Educational advancement process in tertiary institutions in Nigeria. A fellow up study should be embarked upon to determine the sustainability of the training proceeds among undergraduates in tertiary institutions.

Recommendations

It therefore, recommended thus:

- Creative thinking should be encouraged in all tiers? Education in Nigerian through the teaching of convergent, divergent and inspirational thinking skills.
- Female students should be exposed to divergent thinking skills as the finding of this study revealed lower divergent thinking skills amongst them.

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